

Estonian Dependency Treebank and its annotation scheme

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Abstract

In this article, we present Estonian Dependency Treebank, an ongoing corpus annotation project. The size of the treebank, once finished, will be ca 400,000 words. The treebank annotation consists of three layers: morphology, syntactic functions and dependency relations. For each layer, an overview of the labels and the annotation scheme is given.

As for the actual treebank creation, each text is annotated by two independent annotators, plus a super-annotator, whose task is to solve the discrepancies. The article also gives a short overview of the most frequent sources of dissensions between the annotators.

1 Introduction

The Estonian Dependency Treebank (EDT) is an ongoing annotation project which aims at creating a 400,000-word corpus annotated for dependency syntactic structures by the end of the year 2014. By the end of November 2014, we had completed the annotation of all texts, and were working on comparing annotated versions and solving discrepancies.

In the past, few attempts have been made to create an Estonian treebank. The first syntactic analyser of Estonian, a surface-syntactic Constraint Grammar Parser, was finished by 2001 [6]. Simultaneously, a corpus annotated in this framework was created. In order to convert this corpus into a treebank, phrase structure rules were applied and the output was checked manually [2]; this work resulted in a smallish treebank (Arborest).

These experiments showed clearly that although a phrase structure grammar suits well for representing an Estonian noun phrase, Estonian as a typical non-configurational language has no proper verb phrase and components of a multiword

verb may be separated from each other by intervening constituents. The word order (constituent order) is determined mainly by information structure; the main word order rule being that the finite verb occupies the second position in the clause. The word order inside a noun phrase, on the other hand, is fixed. It is generally believed that dependency representation is more suitable for free word order languages [8].

While creating the EDT, every text in the treebank is labelled by two annotators, and a super-annotator compares the versions and solves the discrepancies. No special software is used for annotation, but we have scripts for converting the treebank into CoNLL data format, that enables to use MaltParser tools for detecting formal errors in annotation, e.g. cycles, missing or redundant root-node [9, 1]. In addition, we can thus use MaltEval visualization tool [7].

2 Annotation

The annotation has separate layers for morphology, surface syntax and dependency relations. In the following subsections, we will provide a more detailed discussion of these layers.

2.1 Morphological tagset and syntactic labels

The morphological annotation layer contains information about lemma, part of speech and grammatical categories (e.g. case and number for nominals; mood, tense, person and number for verbs) for every word-form in the text¹. EDT morphological annotation scheme is somewhat different from Universal Dependencies Scheme² (UDS): EDT lacks POS tag for determiners (substituted by pronouns) and also some universal features like gender, animacy, aspect, definiteness or state.

Surface-syntactic layer contains the syntactic function labels. According to our annotation scheme, the members of the verbal chain can be finite or infinite main verbs (FMV, IMV), and finite or infinite auxiliaries (FCV, ICV). Also, we distinguish particles as parts of particle verb (VPart), and verb negators (NEG). The arguments of the verb are labelled as subject (SUBJ), object (OBJ), predicative (PRD) or adverbial (ADV); the adjuncts also get the adverbial label. In addition, the attributes of a nominal are tagged according to their part-of-speech (AN, NN, KN, PN, DN etc). We distinguish the nouns governed by an adposition with a special label (<P or P>) and also nouns governed by a quantor (<Q or Q>). In contrast to the UDS, we analyse adpositions and quantors as heads and the heads of their nominal dependants get special surface-syntactic tag. There is a special symbol for indicating whether the word form is a pre- or postmodifier (<NN or NN> for example). Also, we label conjunctions (J) and interjections (I).

¹A table containing all the morphological tags can be found here: <http://www.cl.ut.ee/korpused/morfliides/seletus.php?lang=en>

²<http://universaldependencies.github.io/docs/>

The main shortcoming of our annotation scheme is that we do not distinguish between adverbial modifiers and adverbial complements. The syntactic layer is shallow, meaning that no virtual nodes are postulated. EDT does not have equivalents for various other core relations described in UDS, for example indirect object (iobj), relations indicating passive (nsubjpass, auxpass) or clausal counterparts (csubj, ccomp) and also loose joining relations as the list, remnant and different kinds of clausal modifier tags. In order to express these relations, more general tags are used in EDT.

Dependency layer gives information about the governor of every word form in the text.

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"<Hoolimata>"          % despite
  "hoolimata" L0 K pre cap <el> @ADVL #1->11
"<köhast>"             % cough
  "köha" Lst S com sg el @<P #2->1
"<ja>"                 % and
  "ja" L0 J crd @J #3->5
"<kõrgest>"           % high
  "kõrge" Lst A pos sg el @AN> #4->5
"<palavikust>"        % fever
  "palavik" Lst S com sg el @<P #5->2
"<ei>"                 % not
  "ei" L0 V aux neg @NEG #6->7
"<saanud>"            % could
  "saa" Lnud V mod indic impf ps neg <NGP-P> @FCV #7->11
"<ta>"                 % he
  "tema" L0 P pers ps3 sg nom @SUBJ #8->11
"<ettekannet>"        % presentation
  "ette_kanne" Lt S com sg part @OBJ #9->11
"<ära>"                % particle
  "ära" L0 D @Vpart #10->11
"<jätta>"              % cancel
  "jät" La V main inf <NGP-P> <PhVerb> <ära> @IMV #11->0
"<>"
  "." Z Fst @Z #12->11

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Figure 1: Sample annotated sentence “In spite of cough and high fever he could not cancel the presentation”.

An example in Fig. 1 demonstrates the use of tags in EDT format. The word forms are in separate rows following their morphological and syntactic description. The description consists of the lemma, ending, POS, morphological information, valency information (between angle brackets), syntactic label (starting with @) and dependency information (starting with #). The first word form *Hoolimata* is

adposition (K), preposition (pre), starting with capital letter (cap), its dependants should be in elative case (<el>), it is functioning as an adverbial and depends on the word form in the position 11 (#1->11). The second word form *kõhast* is substantive (S), singular (sg), elative (el), it belongs to the preposition phrase (@<P) as a head of a noun phrase and it depends on the word form in the position 1 (#2->1).

2.2 Annotation scheme

In general, our annotation scheme is quite coarse for annotating intra-clausal phenomena, and comparable to the Stanford annotation scheme [3]. It should also be kept in mind that a lot of information that the Stanford tagset presents explicitly in the form of syntactic labels, we present as a combination of morphological and syntactic labels. For example, we do not distinguish between coordinating and subordinating conjunctions on the level of syntactic labels, but this information is presented at the morphological level with two different POS-labels: *J crd* and *J sub*. But while annotating the dependency relations that hold between the clauses, we neither distinguish clausal subjects, clausal complements, nor clausal modifiers, and we only state that there is a dependency relation between the clauses.

As McDonald et al [4] have pointed out, common divergences among dependency treebanks are found in the analysis of coordination, verbal chains, subordinate clauses and multiword expressions.

We annotate all coordinated sentence elements using the same syntactic function label. As for dependencies, we annotate each following coordinated element as a dependant of the previous one, and the coordinating conjunction as the dependant of the coordinated element following the conjunction.

While annotating the verb group consisting of a finite auxiliary verb and an infinite lexical verb, there are two possible solutions. Firstly, one can handle the finite auxiliary verb form as the governor of the verb phrase. The other possibility is to treat the infinite lexical verb form as the governor. In our work, we have chosen the second option, since the lexical verb determines the presence and coding of the arguments in the clause. This is consistent with the principle of primacy of content words in UDS.

We connect subordinate clauses to the main clause by attaching the governing verb of the subordinate clause to the governing verb of the main clause. As for coordinated clauses, we follow the overall principles for annotating coordination and annotate them in the same way. We do not actually distinguish between subordination and coordination at the clause level, apart from one exception: the relative clauses are governed by the noun they are modifying.

In EDT, we have treated multiword names as head-final noun phrases that consist of nouns having the part-of-speech tag of a proper noun. So, again, in our annotation scheme the information is spread between the syntactic and morphology layers. As for other types of multiword expressions, we are currently recognizing only particle verbs, a frequent phenomenon in Estonian.

- (3) Kõige olulisem ülesanne on haiglavõrgu korrastamine.
Most important task is hospital network arrangement
'Most important task is an arrangement of the network of hospitals.'

Common sources of disagreement on dependency relations are particles (e.g. *ikka* 'still, again', *veel* 'yet, again', *just* 'just', *muidugi* 'of course' etc) that can function both as sentence and phrase adverbials. Deciding on their proper governor often depends on semantics or even on the information structure of the sentence and that of the neighbouring sentences.

Also, in some cases it is difficult to decide upon the exact governor of a modifier in a long noun phrase, e.g. in example (4) it is hard to decide whether the participle *kujunenud* 'evolved' modifies the word form *liitude* 'unions' or *süsteem* 'system', did the unions or the system evolve during the last decades.

- (4) Vana sajandi viimastel aastakümnetel kujunenud liitude süsteem ei
Old century last decades evolved unions system not
olnud veel lõplik.
was yet final
'The system of unions that evolved during the last decades of the past century was not final yet.'

3 Conclusions and further developments

The Estonian Treebank has been a long sought resource, and although it has been implemented during the last two years, many preliminary ideas for its creation existed before. The construction of a treebank has instigated many discussions, and a number of disputable issues have surfaced about the structure of Estonian and its representation in dependency format. We have tried to keep the annotation in such a format that it could be semi-automatically converted, if needed.

We have already used the beta version of our treebank for parser development. It has been used for improving an existing rule-based parser, training MaltParser and experimenting with various ways to combine those two [5].

After completing the first version of EDT, we plan to continue our efforts to harmonize and elaborate its annotation. Our immediate goals include re-labelling dependency links between subclauses and introducing distinct labels for sentence and phrasal adverbials.

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